

RESEARCH ON THE INHIBITION EFFICIENCY OF CORROSION INHIBITORS BASED ON OLIGOMERS CONTAINING NITROGEN AND SULFUR

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Abstract. *In this article, the physico-chemical properties and level of corrosion protection of nitrogen- and sulfur-retaining oligomers based on gossypol resin have been studied and the possibility of their use in industrial enterprises has been studied. As a result, it was found that the IR-spectrum indicators characterizing corrosion inhibitors contain nitrogen and sulfur bonds, and it was found that their use is effective in protecting against corrosion of open and closed atmospheres in aqueous environments.*

Keywords: *gossypol resin, physical and chemical properties, corrosion inhibitors, concentration, metal structure.*

Result and discussion: Corrosion inhibitors are widely used in the energy, oil and gas processing, metallurgy, mining and quarrying industries, and utilities, including water treatment. In these industries, they are used to stop or control corrosion processes, as well as to treat contaminated water. As a result of today's global economic difficulties, all manufacturing enterprises are focusing on technological equipment for longer service life.

Despite its widespread use in a wide range of industries, steel is highly susceptible to corrosion and can become unusable when exposed to water and acids. For example, steel boilers, metal structures, and turbofans are among the most common challenges to use and extend their service life. Therefore, it is necessary to develop various programs for the protection of corrosion to ensure the continuity of industrial enterprises [1; 2].

In developed countries, along with the use of highly efficient production technologies, great attention is being paid to the widespread use of polymer coatings, water-soluble corrosion inhibitors, corrosion-resistant ceramic materials, polymer composite materials, and corrosion-resistant alloys in these industries to protect metal structures from corrosion. The use of these materials reduces the corrosion process and improves the demand for technological equipment renewal [3; 4].

Figure 1 below shows the global demand for corrosion inhibitors to reach \$7 billion in 2020, with corrosion inhibitors worth 11.3 billion US dollars by 2023. The production of corrosion inhibitors in value shows that the demand for these products is increasing [5].

When analyzing the demand for corrosion inhibitors, the production of corrosion inhibitors based on organic compounds is leading. The main reason for this is the growth of organic corrosion inhibitors due to the negative impact of corrosion inhibitors on the environment, which can release various harmful substances into the environment [6; 7].

Based on the gossypol resin we offer, the physico-chemical properties and level of corrosion protection of oligomers containing nitrogen and sulfur have been studied and it is recommended that they can be used in industrial enterprises.

Based on gossypol resin, nitrogen and sulfur-containing oligomers were obtained at a temperature of 165°C and a time of 2 hours. In order to determine the most optimal conditions for the oligomer formation process, various mass ratios of the starting materials and different temperature parameters were used, as shown in Figure 2, and the yield was found to be 80-85% during experiments.

Figure 1. Increasing demand for corrosion inhibitors in the world (billion US dollars).

Figure 2. Temperature dependence of yield of oligomers containing nitrogen and sulfur based on gossypol resin.

During practical experiments, in order to analyze the information about the composition and location of functional groups of the obtained oligomer containing nitrogen and sulfur based on gossypol resin, the IR spectrum of the sample was obtained and analyzed. In particular, absorption lines characteristic of the -CO-NH₂ functional group were detected in the absorption lines in the 1654-1620 cm⁻¹ range of the IR spectrum of the sample, and absorption lines characteristic of the SO₂- functional group were detected in the 1436-1406 cm⁻¹ range (Fig. 3).

In the course of practical experiments, the analysis of the IR-spectrum indicators of the oligomer sample obtained on the basis of gossypol resin shows that as a result of the reaction, an oligomer containing an amine group and sulfur was formed.

The metal inhibition properties of the synthesized corrosion inhibitors in aqueous media were studied. Laboratory tests to study the inhibition efficiency and protection levels of the synthesized corrosion inhibitors were carried out in sealed containers with a capacity of 500 ml. An electrochemical method was used to determine the inhibition efficiency, and the time of the

laboratory tests was 3 hours. The inhibition mechanism and effectiveness of corrosion inhibitors were studied using polarization curves using a CC-350 potentiostat device. Using this method, it is possible to determine the inhibition efficiency of the surface of the metal electrode from the difference between the potentials of the metal sample in the medium with and without the inhibitor. In environments with a corrosion inhibitor, we can see that the amount of corrosion current is significantly reduced due to the inhibition of the surface of the metal electrode. Electrochemical experiments were carried out on samples of metal St3 steel in the form of plates. A solution of Ag/AgCl was used as a standard electrode. Inhibitors were used in concentrations of 1-3%.

Figure 3. IR-spectrum indicators of the oligomer sample containing nitrogen and sulfur obtained on the basis of gossypol resin.

It was found that the corrosion current value of the solution containing the synthesized corrosion inhibitors varied depending on the type of inhibitor and the environment. This value decreased with increasing concentration of corrosion inhibitors.

Figure 4. Polarization curves of St3 grade steel sample recorded for 3 hours at 303 ± 1 °C in aqueous medium with different concentrations of nitrogen- and sulfur-retaining corrosion inhibitor based on Gossypol resin.

As can be seen from Figure 4, the curves shifted towards the downstream density in the presence of inhibitors, which indicates that the inhibition efficiency of the corrosion inhibitor, is higher in the aqueous environment.

With increasing concentration of the synthesized inhibitor in the test medium, the curves of the current density decrease were observed on both the anodic and cathodic sides. However, the corrosion values and surface slopes remained almost unchanged. According to research, the synthesized corrosion inhibitor simultaneously reduces the dissolution of metal at the anode and the release of hydrogen at the cathode to the corrosion process and acts as a mixed type inhibitor. From this result, it can be seen that the adsorbed inhibitors show inhibition efficiency by blocking the metal surface.

Thus, it was determined that the use of nitrogen and sulfur-retaining corrosion inhibitors based on gossypol resin is effective in protecting against open and closed atmospheric corrosion in aqueous environments.

REFERENCES

1. Bulatov A.I. Ecology in the construction of oil and gas wells: textbook for university students / A.I. Bulatov et al. – Krasnodar: OOO Enlightenment-South, 2011. – 603 p.
2. Bulatov A.I. Asphalt-resin-paraffin deposits and hydrate formation: prevention and removal: in 2 vol.: training manual /A.I. Bulatov, G.V. Kusov, O.V. Savenok. Krasnodar: Publishing House – South, 2011. Vol. 1–2.
3. Фролова Е.А., Кондаков Д.Ф., Орлова В.Т., Авдюшкина Л.И., Быков А.В., Данилов В.П. Разработка противогололедных реагентов на основе формиатов, ацетатов и нитратов щелочных и щелочноземельных металлов и аммония //Химическая технология. 2012. Т. 13. №5. С. 257-262
4. Есина М.Н., Цыганкова Л.Е., Плотникова С.В., Кудрявцева Н.М. Исследование эффективности ингибиторов коррозии серии «Инкоргаз» в модельной пластовой воде М1 //Вестник ТГУ. 2014. Т. 19. №1. С. 161-168.
5. Галямов И.И., Галимов М.Р., Андриянов О.П. Моделирование начальной стадии формирования защитного слоя ингибитора коррозии методом молекулярной динамики //Автоматизация, телемеханизация и связь в нефтяной промышленности. 2011. №9. С. 44-45.
6. Жаксыбаева А.Г., Хамитова А.С. Ингибиторы коррозии для сохранения металлических изделий. Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. 2014. №12-1. С.23-26.
7. В.В. Olimov, N.J. Yo`ldosheva. Gravimetric study of the mechanism of action of corrosion inhibitors used in the oil and gas industry. Международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал «Образование и наука в XXI веке». Выпуск №19 (том 2) (октябрь, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 31.10.2021.